

EVALUATION OF ONLINE CLASSROOM OBSERVATION UTILIZING CLASS OBSERVATION TOOL: A PROPOSED METHODS IN THE TIMES OF UNCERTAINTIES PROGRAM

¹RIZALINO F. MARTE, ²LYNDON A. QUINES, (EdD)

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges, Graduate School

Pioneer Avenue, General Santos City, Philippines

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7561927>

Published Date: 23-January-2023

Abstract: The purpose of this study was to evaluate the online classroom observations of the teachers utilizing the classroom observation tool. The study employed descriptive-evaluative research design. The researcher chose forty-five teachers of H. N Cahilnot Elementary School, Romana C. Acharon Central Elementary School and General Santos City SPED Center as the respondents of the study. The data were gathered using a validated evaluation tool or questionnaire. The findings revealed that teachers are at high level in terms of applying knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas; planning and delivering teaching strategies that are responsive to the special education needs of learners in difficult circumstances including: geographic isolation, chronic illness, displacement due to armed conflict, urban resettlement or disasters, child abuse and child labor practices, and at high level also in terms of selecting, developing, organizing and using appropriate teaching and learning resources including ICT to address learning goals. Overall, the teachers are at high level in the online classroom observations. Based on the results of the study, an intervention program was designed to help teachers further improve their teaching pedagogies.

Keywords: Educational management, online classroom observation, classroom observation tools, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditional teachers' class observation program is more direct in terms of feedback. Online class observation can feel more isolated. It is not easy to invite a fellow faculty member to observe an online class, and getting an immediate response from the learners can be difficult when they are physically removed and behind their computer screens. Measures of Effective Teaching data contributes to growing evidence that observation ratings, used as part of comprehensive teacher evaluation systems across the nation, may measure factors outside of a teacher's performance or control (Bartanen & Kwok, 2021; Campbell & Ronfeldt, 2018; Jeffery & Bauer, 2020; Kaymakamoglu, 2018).

The world is still dealing with the ongoing crisis caused by the pandemic, and education remains online for the foreseeable future. There have been rapid online development and problems in how online education is taught. The changes in the system of education have hit schools very hard. The unthinkable happened suddenly. The entire education system has had

to shift online. Globally over 1.2 billion learners were out of the classroom. As a result, education has changed dramatically with the remarkable rise of e-learning, whereby teaching is undertaken remotely and on digital platforms or online learning. With the shift of traditional education platforms to online, teachers are still expected to deliver quality teaching among the learners. Thus, the online class observation remained utilized to evaluate the teaching and learning process and teachers' overall performances as well (De Vera, Manalo, Ermeno, Carolyn, & Elores, 2022; Li & Lalani, 2020).

Classroom observation is essential because it is a vital tool for teacher development and evaluation. It often carries considerable weight in teacher appraisal and improvement systems and provides the critical formative anchor informing professional development. Further, the most important reason to conduct classroom observation is to educate teachers on professional development and, subsequently, to know if it is working. Observational methods can also be inquiry-driven, investigating classroom processes to generate hypotheses about their impact on learning (Bell, Dobbelaer, Klette & Visscher, 2019; Cohen & Goldhaber, 2016; Martinez, Taut & Schaaf, 2016).

For instance, in the United States, a classroom observation is a technique of monitoring teaching activity directly as it happens in real-time, taking notes and coding instructional activities in the classroom or from video lessons by the observer or analyst. While the methodology is commonly used throughout the educational continuum, in K-12 schools, where protocols such as the Classroom Appraisal Scoring System and the Teaching Structure are used for teacher assessment, the methodological complexity is more pronounced (Bell, Dobbelaer, Klette & Visscher, 2019; Dieker, Straub, Hynes, Hughes, Bukathy, Bousfield & Mrstik, 2019; Martinez, Taut & Schaaf, 2016).

In the Philippines, the school heads and master teachers are still required to conduct classroom observations through an online platform as mandated by the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). Working for the online class has many difficulties in teaching and learning during the COVID-19 crisis. There was the unstable internet connectivity; inadequate learning resources; electric power interruptions; vague learning contents; overloaded lesson activities; limited teacher scaffolds; poor peer communication; conflict with home responsibilities; poor learning environment; related financial problems; physical health compromises; and mental health struggles (Caratiquit & Pablo, 2021; Reyes-Chua, Remollo-Mack & Vloria, 2019; Rotas & Cahapay, 2020).

In H.N Cahilsot Central Elementary School, when school heads and master teachers conduct observations, one of the issues they frequently encounter is that teachers fail to apply content knowledge within and across curriculum teaching areas; plan and deliver teaching strategies that are responsive to the special education needs of learners under challenging circumstances such as geographic isolation, chronic illness, displacement due to armed conflict, urban resettlement, or disasters. Thus, as the learning delivery changes, the duties of teachers must be captured in their performance assessment through a more contextualized Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS), most especially in the teaching-learning process. From this lens, there is an urgency to evaluate the online classroom observation by utilizing the class observation tool, knowing that there was a sudden shift from face-to-face to online learning mode.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the online classroom observations among selected public elementary schools in the General Santos City Division.

Specifically, this sought answers to the following research objectives:

1. To determine the level of online classroom observations among elementary schools in General Santos City in terms of:
 - 1.1 Applying knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas;
 - 1.2 Planning and delivering teaching strategies that are responsive to the special education needs of learners under challenging circumstances, including geographic isolation, chronic illness, displacement due to armed conflict, urban resettlement or disasters, child abuse, and child labor practices;
 - 1.3 Are you selecting, developing, organizing, and using appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals?
2. To determine what intervention program can be made based on the study's results.

Theoretical Framework

The study utilized different theoretical frameworks that could be used to structure the discussion on when the public-school teachers retire early. The undertaking of the present study is based on the summit of the following theoretical framework on retirement theories:

This study is based on the Scaffolding and peers tutoring cognitive learning theories. The cognitive theories of Piaget and Vygotsky 1997 have significantly influenced the theory and practice of education worldwide. According to the theorists, knowledge, and comprehension are dynamically created by the developing person himself for the outward information instead of inactively absorbing it.

Moreover, learning is best conceived as a process, not in outcomes. The primary focus should be on engaging students in a process that best enhances their understanding. This process includes feedback on the effectiveness of their learning efforts, and education must be conceived as a continuing reconstruction of experience. The process and goal of education are the same (De Vera, Manalo, Ermeno, Carolyn & Elores, 2022; Patton, 2017; Sloat, Amrein-Beardsley & Holloway, 2018).

Another proposition states that peer tutoring is beneficial for academic development but also helpful for improvement in one's attitude and motivation to learn. Vygotsky believed that peers play a very significant role in the development of a person. The healthy relationship between peers and children allows a better kind of personal investigation and exploration. A person internalizes new thinking patterns due to interaction with peers (Mishra & Mehta, 2017; Pianta & Hamre, 2017; Topping, 2017).

Furthermore, while it is clear that teachers must be trained to teach effectively with technology, whether synchronous (real-time) e-learning (as to video conferencing, live text or audio chat, etc. or asynchronous (at one's own pace) e-learning (such as email) should be used for such training is unclear. For students who prefer the flexibility and privacy that asynchronous platforms provide, synchronous learning can be inconvenient and scary. According to several research studies, synchronous e-learners have more continuous communication, more attention to tasks, increased involvement, and more frequent completion of work and courses than their asynchronous counterparts (Farinella, Hobbs & Weeks, 2017; Goldhaber, 2016; Kolb & Kolb, 2021).

Due to advancements in information communication technology (ICT), increased use of the Internet, and postsecondary institutions' attempts to reduce costs associated with classroom instruction, E-learning is now an established and growing practice in postsecondary trade school, college, or university education (E-learning is becoming embedded into Australian postsecondary institutions in particular; Australia is a world leader in online education, followed by countries such as the United States (Babalola & Hafsatu, 2016; Chism, 2017; Gall, Borg & Gall, 2017).

2. METHOD

The researcher used a quantitative approach in this study, specifically a descriptive-evaluative study design. An evaluation is a process that examines it critically. It entails gathering and analyzing data on the activities, characteristics, and outcomes of a program. Its goal is to make program evaluations, improve program effectiveness, and inform programming decisions (Guarino & Stacy, 2017; Hamzah, Wei, Ahmad, Hamid & Mansor, 2018; Patton, 2017).

Descriptive research also has the goal of describing a phenomenon and its characteristics. This study is more interested in what happened rather than how or why. As a result, data is frequently gathered through observation and survey methods. Data may be collected qualitatively in such studies, but it is commonly analyzed with frequencies, percentages, averages, and other statistical analyses used to determine relationships (Babalola & Hafsatu, 2016; Chism, 2017; Gall, Borg & Gall, 2017).

On the other hand, the research method is quantitative; this means a concept, a definition, metaphors, symbols, and a description of things. This definition demonstrates that qualitative research includes all the necessary instruments for eliciting recall, which aids in problem-solving (Alawamleh, Al-Twait, & Al-Saht, 2020; Caratiquit, 2021).

The research method, on the other hand, is quantitative. Meanings, concepts, definitions, metaphors, symbols, and descriptions of things describe qualitative research. This definition demonstrates that qualitative research includes all the necessary instruments for eliciting recall, which aids problem-solving. A computer can calculate and conduct data (numbers, percentages, and measurable figures) using a statistical package for social science (SPSS), which saves a lot of time and resources (Gall, Borg & Gall, 2017; Gurung, 2021; Impof, 2020).

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp: (60-74), Month: January - February 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

This approach also allows for generalization due to scientific methods for data collection and analysis. It is possible to generalize interactions with a single group. The interpretation of research findings, while similar, does not have to be viewed as a coincidence. In terms of samples, contents, and patterns, the study of problem-solving instruction in secondary school science education within one specific area or zone can reflect the larger society (Bowering, Mills & Merritt, 2017; Francisco, 2021; Goldhaber, 2016).

The research was conducted in General Santos City Division, specifically in H.N Cahilsot Central Elementary School-Cahilsot district, Romana C. Acharon Central Elementary School- Romana C. Acharon District, and General Santos City SPED Integrated School- Pedro C. Acharon District.

The study occurred in Barangay Calumpang and San Isidro, both located in General Santos City.

The respondents of this study were the teachers in General Santos City Division. Specifically, eight teachers in H.N Cahilsot Elementary School, 8 Romana C. Acharon Central Elementary School, and 29 teachers in General Santos City SPED Integrated School. A total of 45 teachers were involved as the respondents.

The total number of respondents in this study is 45. These are the teachers who have experienced conducting classes online wherein their observers used Classroom Observation Tools to rate them

The study used universal sampling. It means that the entire population of teachers in different districts, such as Cahilsot, Romana C. Acharon, and Pedro C. Acharon, including the three schools who had experienced online class observations in the new normal situation.

A Classroom Observation Tool (COT) was used by the Department of Education to evaluate the online classroom observations conducted by the teachers as observed by the school leaders. A Classroom Observation Tool (COT) was used by the Department of Education was utilized. It was subjected to experts' validation processes. Five experts will validate the questionnaire.

The five-point Likert scale was used for the research variables. According to Santos (2007), the Likert Scale requires individuals to tick on a box/blank in response to many items concerning an attitude, object, and stimulus. It is common to treat the number obtained from a rating scale directly as measurements by calculating averages or, more generally, any arithmetic operations.

Identified experts validated the prepared questionnaires. Before using the questionnaire, the researcher ensured that all comments and suggestion were incorporated in the final revision of the questionnaire.

For the successful conduct of the study, the following steps were followed by the researcher:

First, the researcher secured a letter of approval from the Dean of the Graduate School. Another authorization note was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent, Public Schools District Supervisor of three Districts, to the principal of HN Cahilsot ES, Calumpang ES, Romana C. Acharon Central Elementary School, and General Santos City SPED Integrated School.

Second, the researcher ensured that a group of experts had already validated the questionnaires used in the study. Experts used a validation tool to assess the reliability and validity of the questionnaires prepared accurately. It was to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data.

The researcher prepared all the necessary questionnaires after obtaining the required documents. They were printed in black and white. In addition, the researcher ensured that the teachers' right to confidentiality and data privacy, as mandated by the Data Privacy Act, is given top priority in this study. They were not forced to reveal their real names and could use code names to maintain their anonymity.

The researchers and respondents followed all health protocols the Department of Health set forth while conducting the study. The respondents wore face masks and face shields. Their hands were sanitized regularly and observed two-meter physical or social distance.

The accomplished questionnaires' results were verified, checked, and tallied. After the results had been calculated and validated, data were analyzed and interpreted to address the objectives of this study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered about the evaluation of online classroom observation utilizing class observation tools as the basis for an intervention program. Results are shown in the succeeding tables coupled with textual discussions.

Table 1 presents the content knowledge application across teaching areas with corresponding mean and descriptive equivalent and discussions.

Table 1: Apply knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas

Item	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
The teacher explains concepts and makes no content errors.	4.42	Very High
The teacher demonstrates factual knowledge of the subject matter and attempts to connect content across teaching areas.	3.60	High
The teacher displays a comprehensive understanding of the concepts and structure of the teaching area.	3.98	High
The teacher presents conceptual knowledge of the subject and makes connections within the teaching area.	3.91	High
The teacher addresses content accurately, and its focus is congruent with the teaching area's big ideas and structure.	4.33	Very High
The teacher applies extensive content knowledge beyond their area of specialization.	3.51	High
The teacher motivates learners to investigate the teaching area to expand their knowledge and satisfy their curiosity.	3.96	High
The teacher cites intra and interdisciplinary content relationships.	3.84	High
The teacher shows expertise in the content and uses appropriate pedagogy in delivering the lesson.	3.76	High
Overall	3.92	High

It could be gleaned from the table that with a mean of 4.42, the teachers are at a very high level in clearly explaining concepts and making no content errors. With a mean of 3.60, the teachers are at a high level in demonstrating factual knowledge of the subject matter and attempting to connect content across teaching areas. Also, with a mean of 3.98, the teachers are at a high level in terms of displaying a comprehensive understanding of the concepts and structure of the content areas.

Additionally, with the mean of 3.91, the teachers are at a high level in presenting conceptual knowledge of the subject and making connections within teaching areas. With a mean of 4.33, the teachers are at a very high level in accurately addressing content, and its focus is congruent with the teaching area's big ideas and structure. With a mean of 3.51, the teachers are at a high level in applying extensive knowledge of content beyond their area of specialization. With a mean of 3.96, the teachers are at a high level in motivating learners to investigate the teaching area to expand their knowledge and satisfy their curiosity.

On the other hand, with the mean of 3.84, the teachers are at a high level in terms of citing intra and interdisciplinary content relationships. Lastly, with a mean of 3.76, the teachers are at a high level in showing expertise in the content and using appropriate pedagogy in delivering the lesson. Overall, with an overall mean of 3.92, the teachers are at a high level in applying knowledge across curriculum and teaching areas.

Thus, in a single measure, analysts can determine whether or not a teacher's practice is aligned with the best practices, as specified by particular criteria. Yet caution should be exercised in using evaluative protocols for two reasons. First, evaluative measures may turn off or alienate faculty and thus may be of limited utility for professional development. Second, reliability is rugged when analysts must describe teaching and judge its quality in real-time. A recent review of the reliability of evaluative protocols used in K-12 settings found that ratings varied considerably and that rater bias as to pre-existing beliefs about what constitutes high-quality teaching) is a significant reason for the high degree of variability observed in using these protocols.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp: (60-74), Month: January - February 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Table 2 presents the planning and delivering teaching strategies that are responsive to the special education needs of learners in challenging circumstances, including geographic isolation, chronic illness, displacement due to armed conflict, urban resettlement, child abuse, and child labor practices.

Table 2: Planning and delivering teaching strategies

Item	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
The teacher displays familiarity with learners' backgrounds but sometimes lacks responsiveness in addressing them.	4.33	Very High
To inform instructions, the teacher understands the purpose and value of learning about learners' backgrounds.	4.24	Very High
The teacher provides thoughtful and appropriate instructional adaptation for individual learner needs. The transformation of instruction is realistic and practical.	4.09	High
The teacher provides diverse learners opportunities to engage in various learning activities actively.	4.29	Very High
The teacher demonstrated a broader understanding of the learner's educability of individual learners.	4.16	High
Teacher instructional strategies respond to individual and group learners' backgrounds, thus creating an environment where learners feel equally involved.	4.00	High
Overall	3.69	High

It could be noted that with a mean of 4.33, the teachers are at a very high level in terms of familiarity with learners' backgrounds but sometimes lack responsiveness in addressing them. With the mean of 4.24, the teachers are at a very high level in demonstrating an understanding of the purpose and valuing of learning about learners' backgrounds to inform instructions. Additionally, with a mean of 4.09, the teachers are at a high level in providing thoughtful and appropriate instructional adaptation for individual learner needs.

The adaptation of instruction is realistic and practical. Also, with a mean of 4.29, the teachers are at a very high level in providing diverse learners with opportunities to engage in various learning activities actively. With a mean of 4.16, the teachers are at a high level when it comes to demonstrating a broader understanding of the learner's educability of individual learners. Lastly, with a mean of 4.0, the teachers are at a high level in responding to individual and group learners' backgrounds, thus creating an environment where learners feel equally involved. Finally, with an overall mean of 3.69, the teachers are at a high level in terms of planning and delivering teaching strategies that are responsive to the special education needs of learners in challenging circumstances, including geographic isolation, chronic illness, displacement due to armed conflict, urban resettlement or disasters, child abuse, and child labor practices.

It is supported by the idea that quality education depends on implementing instructional supervision, especially in the public elementary and secondary schools, as part of the duties and functions of instructional supervisors. Instructional supervisors perform varied roles in the improvement and development of curriculum instruction. Instructional supervisors, both internal and external to the school, are tasked to do supervisory work and carry out supervisory functions to help teachers improve learning conditions. As a result, there were improvements in the quality of instruction and academic performance in learning institutions. In this connection, the progress of students' academic achievement is the measure of adequate supervision.

Table 3 presents selecting, developing, organizing, and using appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals with the mean and descriptive equivalent and discussion of the results.

Table 3: Selecting, developing, organizing, and using appropriate teaching and learning resources

Item	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
The teacher utilizes various instructional materials and resources aligned with the instructional purposes, which permanently support the learning goals.	3.64	High
The teacher skillfully manages diverse instructional materials encompassing other disciplines that consistently support learning goals.	3.84	High
Overall	3.74	High

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp: (60-74), Month: January - February 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

The results could conclude that the teachers are at a high level in utilizing various instructional materials and resources aligned with the instructional purposes that consistently support the learning goals. Also, with the mean of 3.84, the teachers are at a high level in skillfully managing diverse instructional materials encompassing other disciplines that consistently support the learning goals. Lastly, with an overall mean of 3.74, the teachers are at a high level in selecting, developing, organizing, and using appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals.

Also, carrying out an in-class teaching observation is a precious practice. Participants in the CTSI mentorship research also suggested that this formative in-class observational feedback be treated independently from statements made as part of formal summative tenure and promotion processes. Some divisions require that faculty members be observed teaching as part of the application process for tenure or promotion and that a report on the in-class observation is presented to the review committee. Participants reported little preparation or feedback on in-class instruction before this observation. In such circumstances, preparation may involve a formative "check-in" before the more formalized statement.

Table 4: Summary of Evaluation of Online Classroom Observation Utilizing Class Observation Tool

Item	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Apply knowledge of content an across curriculum teaching areas	3.92	High
Planning and delivering teaching strategies that are responsive to the special education needs of learners under challenging circumstances, including geographic isolation, chronic illness, displacement due to armed conflict, urban resettlement or disasters, child abuse, and child labor practices	3.69	High
Selecting, developing, organizing, and using appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals	3.74	High
Overall	3.78	High

It could be noted from the results presented above that with an overall mean of 3.92. The teachers are at a high level in terms of Applying knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas. With an overall mean of 3.69, the teachers are at a high level in terms of planning and delivering teaching strategies that are responsive to the special education needs of learners under challenging circumstances, including geographic isolation, chronic illness, displacement due to armed conflict, urban resettlement or disasters, child abuse, and child labor practices. Also, with an overall mean of 3.74, the teachers are at a high level in selecting, developing, organizing, and using appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals. Finally, the weighted mean is 3.78, which means that the teachers are at a high level regarding their online classroom observations when the current classroom observation tool is utilized.

Table 5: MENTORS IN THE TIMES OF UNCERTAINTIES: ACTION PLAN FOR PROGRAM IMPLEMENTATION

CONCEPTS TO BE APPLIED/ SHARED	ACTIVITIES OR PROJECTS & OBJECTIVES	DATE AND DURATION (beginning & ending dates)	HUMAN RESOURC ES NEEDED	FINANCIAL RESOURCES NEEDED	MATE RIALS AND OTHER RESOURCES NEEDED	INDICATORS OF SUC-CESS
1. Conduct an orientation with the teachers regarding the study's results. GURO, IKAW, AND BIDA will be introduced.	Orientation with the teachers who will be the subject of the program.	June 2022	Teachers and the School Principal	3,000.00	• bond papers Markers	100% attendance of the teachers and school heads is manifested.
2. Start planning to conduct a SLAC Session on enhancing teachers' performance during the online class observations.	Plan for the conduct of a School Learning Action Cell.	July 2022	School Head and Speakers	2,000.00	Bond Papers Ink Markers	Monitoring and Evaluation Sheets
3. Implement a 5-hour seminar on teaching pedagogies in the new normal by incorporating it into the School-Based Learning Action Cells in five sessions (SLAC)	Conduct School-Based Learning Action Cells (SLAC)	August 2022	Teachers, school heads, resource speaker	5,000.00	Internet connectivity/Wifi Ink Paper Printer Construction Papers Foods and Accommodation	The outputs of the teachers will be collected.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp: (60-74), Month: January - February 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

This chapter presents the summary of the research work undertaken, the conclusions drawn, and the recommendations made as an outgrowth of this study. This study aimed to evaluate the conduct of Classroom Observations in the Division of General Santos City utilizing the current Classroom Observation Tools in assessing teachers' performance.

Level of online classroom observations among elementary schools in General Santos City

This research aimed to evaluate online classroom observations among elementary schools in the General Santos City division. The findings revealed that teachers are at high in terms of applying content knowledge within and across curriculum teaching areas, with an overall mean of 3.92. It means that teaching in an online class primarily manifests the understanding of content, planning, and delivering teaching strategies.

The proposition supports the results that classroom observation is a method of directly observing teaching practice as it unfolds in real-time, with the observer or analyst taking notes and coding instructional behaviors in the classroom or from videoed lessons. Though widely used across the educational spectrum, the technique is far more common—and the methodological sophistication more pronounced—in K–12 schools, where protocols such as the Classroom Assessment Scoring System and the Framework for Teaching are used for teacher evaluation (De Vera, Manalo, Ermeno, Carolyn & Elores, 2022; Pianta & Hamre, 2017; Suparto, 2020).

Additionally, faculty developers often use classroom observations for coaching and mentoring. Some teaching and learning centers offer services where a trained faculty developer observes a class, often with a structured protocol, and then meets one-on-one with the teacher. Often, faculty developers will not simply conduct a single observation but integrate pre-and post-class interviews or coaching sessions and provide the instructor targeted feedback. Notably, this type of coaching can be performed with various instructional roles, including graduate teaching assistants, tenure-track faculty, and contract lecturers. An essential aspect of using observations for faculty development is to develop a sense of mutual trust between faculty and analysts (Bowering, Mills & Merrit, 2017; Gepila, 2020; Tayag, 2018).

Further, campus teaching and learning centers often use unstructured protocols—where observers take notes during class with no specified direction about what behaviors or facets of teaching to record and in what fashion. This joint approach generally yields rich contextualized information about the observed class. Yet, the variability and lack of standardized data collection procedures negate the possibility of comparing data across raters or cases rated by the same observer. In cases where faculty developers use structured protocols, those that do not require an evaluative judgment on the part of the observer regarding the quality of instruction and instead describe teaching in concrete terms may aid instructors interested in improving their education because it is much more helpful to identify what [instructors] are doing rather of what they should be (Bartley & Golek, 2017; Chism, 2017; Goldhaber, 2016).

Furthermore, using classroom observations as a form of "high-stakes" assessment and evaluation presents several problems, a lesson that has been learned in K–12 settings. Classroom observations have often been used in these settings to complement value-added metrics. However, recent research indicates that while value-added is a limited and variable measure of teacher quality, classroom observations can be equally unreliable (Guarino & Stacy, 2017; Impof, 2020; Law, 2022).

On the other hand, many observation protocols used in both K–12 and postsecondary settings are designed to evaluate the quality of classroom teaching. This judgment can take the form of underlying scales that purport to capture key aspects of high-quality instruction based on either external criteria or latent variables viewed as proxy measures for student achievement. This approach is attractive for those wanting a single action of teaching quality or to determine whether or not learning steps up to particular standards or expectations as to the degree of reformed-ness (Asio & Jimenez, 2020; Blazar, Litke & Barmore, 2016).

Further, professional teacher development is a recommended method for the improvement of not only skill but performance in the classroom environment as well. It also establishes expert teachers and increases their job opportunities and the benefits it will bring their learners. Schools need highly qualified, talented teachers to improve the quality of education, and an advanced degree tells a school you are a valuable, knowledgeable teacher that will have the most impact on your students (Rosier, Slade, Perkins, Baldwin, Coiacetto, Budge & Harwood 2016; Riego de Dios, 2020; Tawalbeh, 2020).

Furthermore, lesson observation is one of the significant functions of supervisors. Supervisors use it as a primary tool to assess teachers' content knowledge and competency in instructional strategies and practices to provide the necessary assistance to improve instruction. Administrators should ensure teachers prepare lesson notes before curricular implementation (Babalola & Hafsatu, 2016; Torch & Rothman, 2018; Weli & Bako-Osu, 2019).

As a matter of fact, as an instructional source, supervisors provide not only a diagnosis of teaching but also feedback that enables teachers' professional growth and development. School heads need to establish a positive work climate. This phase has a significant bearing on the success of supervision and requires qualities like intimacy, honesty, tactfulness, and considerateness alongside mutual understanding from both parties. Exchange of ideas led to teachers' improvement when issues discussed are educational and beneficial, especially regarding classroom practice or management (Babalola & Hafsatu, 2016; Bowering, Mills & Merritt, 2017).

In addition, improving teacher evaluation is one of the most pressing and contested contemporary educational policy issues. There is compelling evidence that teachers represent a key leverage point for improving student outcomes in the short and long term and that teachers vary substantially in their effectiveness. Despite this substantial variation, until recently, most formal teacher evaluations have been cursory and not very discriminating (Caratiquit & Pablo, 2021; Danielson, 2017; Torch & Rothman, 2018).

In particular, many have questioned the use of value-added measures (VAMs) in newer evaluation systems. These measures are controversial for several reasons. First, they have low face validity among educators who question whether standardized tests represent the broader construct of interest, student learning. Teachers also do not always know how to interpret such measures, nor do they provide information teachers can use to identify specific areas for instructional improvement (Dizon, San Pedro, Munsayac, Padilla & Pascual, 2018; Sloat, Amrein-Beardsley & Holloway, 2018).

Additionally, classroom observations, on the other hand, are used nearly universally to assess teachers. They have high levels of face validity because they consider teaching practices that teachers themselves can observe. This information can provide timely and actionable formative feedback for those striving to become better practitioners. Despite these potential benefits, one of the critiques against observations is the precedent of not differentiating among teachers. Observation instruments are criterion-referenced measures, not necessarily leading to a distribution of ratings, and historically most teachers have been deemed practical or highly effective. This lack of differentiation is often referred to as the widget effect (Guarino & Stacy, 2017; Jewell, 2017; Weisberg, Sexton, Mulhern, Keeling, Schunck, Palcisco & Morgan, 2019).

Interestingly, given their prevalent use, we know surprisingly little about the statistical properties of classroom observations in consequential personnel decisions. Indeed, much of what we know is derived from extensive research of a large-scale research study—the Measures of Effective Teaching (MET) Project. It is unclear how these findings might translate when evaluation reform is implemented. Will real-world classroom observations differentiate among teachers? Will they be reliable? Will teachers receive actionable feedback, leading them to seek and receive high-quality professional development? The answers to questions like these are crucial to understanding how observational performance measures will affect the teacher workforce quality (Blazar, Litke & Barmore, 2016; Goldhaber, Lavery & Theobald, 2017).

Also, there are multiple dimensions by which a teacher might be deemed effective. Teachers support students in myriad ways in service of various outcomes, including social and emotional effects. Even if we focus on the narrower construct of teacher effectiveness at helping student learning on academic outcomes, value-added estimates culled from a single test may only represent a portion of the broader construct of interest (Blazar, Litke & Barmore, 2016; Cash, Hamre, Pianta & Myers, 2017).

Moreover, part of the challenge is that instructional quality is inherently situated. Good teaching likely varies in response to contextual factors, including school and district leadership, curricula, and collegial support. So too, might high-quality instruction go for specific populations of students, such as English learners or special education students. Indeed, prior research has demonstrated that student demographics are associated with VAMs and instructional practices (Asio & Riego de Dios, 2019; Blazar, Litke & Barmore, 2016; Tayag, 2018).

Improving teacher evaluation is one of the most pressing and contested contemporary educational policy issues. There is compelling evidence that teachers represent a key leverage point for improving student outcomes in the short and long term and that teachers vary substantially in their effectiveness. Despite this substantial variation, until recently, most formal teacher evaluations have been cursory and not very discriminating (Torch & Rothman, 2018).

In particular, many have questioned the use of value-added measures (VAMs) in newer evaluation systems. These measures are controversial for several reasons. First, they have low face validity among educators who question whether standardized tests represent the broader construct of interest, student learning. Teachers also do not always know how to interpret such measures, nor do they provide information teachers can use to identify specific areas for instructional improvement (Calvin, 2017; Chism, 2017; Sloat, Amrein-Beardsley & Holloway, 2018).

Additionally, classroom observations, on the other hand, are used nearly universally to assess teachers. They have high levels of face validity because they consider teaching practices that teachers themselves can observe. This information can provide timely and actionable formative feedback for those striving to become better practitioners. Despite these potential benefits, one of the critiques against observations is the precedent of not differentiating among teachers. Observation instruments are criterion-referenced measures, not necessarily leading to a distribution of ratings, and historically most teachers have been deemed practical or highly effective. This lack of differentiation is often referred to as the widget effect (Danielson, 2017; Francisco, 2021; Goldhaber & Brown, 2017).

Interestingly, given their prevalent use, we know surprisingly little about the statistical properties of classroom observations in consequential personnel decisions. Indeed, much of what we know is derived from extensive research of a large-scale research study—the Measures of Effective Teaching (MET) Project. It is unclear how these findings might translate when evaluation reform is implemented. Will real-world classroom observations differentiate among teachers? Will they be reliable? Will teachers receive actionable feedback, leading them to seek and receive high-quality professional development? The answers to questions like these are vital in understanding how observational performance measures will affect the teacher workforce quality (Caratiquit, 2021; Gall, Gall & Borg, 2017; Goldhaber, Lavery & Theobald, 2017).

Also, there are multiple dimensions by which a teacher might be deemed effective. Teachers support students in myriad ways in service of various outcomes, including social and emotional effects. Even if we focus on the narrower construct of teacher effectiveness in supporting student learning on academic outcomes, value-added estimates from a single test may only represent a portion of the broader construct of interest (Blazar & Kraft, 2018; Hammersley-Fletcher & Orsmond, 2017).

Moreover, part of the challenge is that instructional quality is inherently situated. Good teaching likely varies in response to contextual factors, including school and district leadership, curricula, and collegial support. So too, might high-quality instruction go for specific populations of students, such as English learners or special education students. Indeed, prior research has demonstrated that student demographics are associated with VAMs and instructional practices (Blazar, Litke, Barmore & Grossman, 2018; Hamzah, 2018).

In addition, several studies show how the peer review model for teaching observation gives possibilities for faculty growth and enhances teaching practice. Observing a colleague can show the observing teachers how new strategies work and improve their confidence to apply them in their teaching. I also demonstrated that teaching observation could provide an opportunity to examine both content and delivery of individual course components so that suggestions as to how these might be improved or refined (Li & Lilani, 2020; Sullivan, Buckle, Nicky & Atkinson, 2017).

Furthermore, other advantages include direct collegial support and increased teaching-related collaboration. Peer observation can serve as a valuable chance for reflection throughout the process, providing insight into teaching practices, joint professional development, and quality improvement in teaching and learning (Topping, 2017; Sullivan, Buckle, Nicky & Atkinson, 2017).

Lastly, according to research, the most successful peer observations for fostering progress in teaching skills entail self-reflection on the part of both the observer and the observe. This reflective approach involves the teaching process and reasoning behind it, rather than merely evaluating the instruction itself." It is thus addressing the question of why rather than how, and it is about learning from this process (Calvin College, 2017; Farniella, Hobbs & Weeks, 2017; Hammersley-Fletcher & Orsmond, 2017).

The actual "brick and mortar" classroom is losing its monopoly as a learning environment. From a global economy and personal and professional networks to sources of information, news, and learning, the Internet and the World Wide Web have substantially altered practically every area of our lives. Online learning is now possible thanks to the Internet. Many researchers and educators, especially in higher education, are interested in adopting online learning to improve student learning outcomes while overcoming resource restrictions. Furthermore, students from all walks of life have increased their

need for online learning. Given the rapid—some might say precipitous—growth of online education and its potential in higher education, researchers and educators must evaluate the effectiveness of online learning in educating students about traditional face-to-face learning. (Farinella, Hobbs & Weeks, 2017; Millis, 2017; Mishra & Mehta, 2017).

Furthermore, online learning is a type of distance learning or distance education that has long been a component of the American educational system and has recently grown to become the most extensive distance learning sector (Bartley & Golek, 2017; Kraft, Blazar & Hogan, 2018).

There is a lot of debate about online learning because it has a lot of potential benefits and applications. The effectiveness in educating students, its use as professional development, its cost-effectiveness in combating rising postsecondary education costs, credit equivalency at the postsecondary level, and the ability to provide a world-class education to anyone with a broadband connection are just a few of the most important. The most attention for online learning has been focused on higher education. The relevance of a college degree and the rising cost of higher education are extensively recognized in the literature (Patton, 2017; Zhang, Li & Harris, 2017).

In addition, the wage gap between high school graduates and college graduates is widening. Simultaneously, college tuition expenses are rising faster than inflation, and student loan debt is rapidly growing. The entire national student loan debt was over one trillion dollars in 2014. Many academics and educators believe that online learning can help to combat rising postsecondary education costs by spreading the price of a class over a much larger number of students than in traditional classrooms, dividing the cost by tens or hundreds of thousands of students rather than a few dozen (Sullivan, Buckle, Nicky & Atkinson, 2017; Pianta & Harme, 2017; Tawalbeh, 2020).

To teach all students according to today's standards, Shulman (1987) claims that teachers must have a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter and the flexibility to assist students in developing meaningful cognitive maps, relate one idea to another, and resolve misconceptions. Teachers must be able to see how ideas interact across disciplines and in daily life. This information is a foundation for pedagogical content knowledge, allowing teachers to communicate concepts to others.

From it, we can say that this allows the student to learn by connecting ideas and concepts across different disciplines. Students learning in this way can apply the knowledge gained in one field to another other domain to deepen the learning experience.

For instance, in the study, teachers are highly applying the teaching across other subjects or what we call the interdisciplinary. It will help address students' differences and helps to develop essential, transferable skills. These skills, such as critical thinking, communication, and analysis, are crucial and continually growing at all stages of life. Thus, educational systems serve students best if they enable and encourage students to build their interdisciplinary pathways. It is sure to foster a love of learning, ignite a spark of enthusiasm, and address learning differences for students.

Meanwhile, teachers are doing a good job planning and delivering teaching strategies that are responsive to the special education needs of learners in challenging situations, such as geographic isolation, chronic illness, displacement due to armed conflict, urban resettlement or disasters, and child abuse, and child labor practices. The teacher displayed material mastery, instructional planning and delivery strategies, and teaching and learning tools throughout the online class.

The Department of Education's Order No. 42, s. According to 2017, the primary function of instructors in creating learning environments sensitive to student variety is in this domain. It emphasizes the importance of instructors' knowledge and awareness of learners' different qualities and experiences, as well as their respect for them, as inputs to the planning and designing of learning opportunities. It emphasizes the importance of varied teaching approaches for all students to be successful citizens in a changing local and global context.

Research has shown that when the learning environment is established, student engagement increases most, especially the students' attention and focus, promotes meaningful learning experiences, encourages higher levels of student performance, and motivates students to practice higher-level critical thinking skills. Further, a positive learning environment is where healthy relationships with peers and teachers flourish (Farinella, Hobbs & Weeks, 2017; Hendry & Oliver, 2017).

Consequently, when it comes to selecting, developing, organizing, and learning goals, the teachers are at a high level, with an overall mean of 3.74. It means that teachers know content, planning and delivering teaching strategies, and teaching and learning resources are in the teacher's online class.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp: (60-74), Month: January - February 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Education improves engagement and knowledge retention: When ICT is integrated into lessons, students become more engaged in their work. It is because technology provides different opportunities to make it more enjoyable to teach the same things in different ways.

It will continue to be a significant part of the future as it connects to more aspects of our lives. It will continually evolve and change because we consumers all like a choice. We like using ICT for personal growth, creativity, joy, consumption, and wealth (Goldhaber & Hansen, 2017; Impof, 2020).

Overall, the teachers are at a high level in the online classroom observations, with an overall mean of 3.78, which indicates that most of the time know the content, plan and deliver teaching strategies, and teaching and learning resources.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alawamleh, M., Al-Twait, L. M., & Al-Saht, G. R. (2020). The effect of online learning on communication between instructors and students during Covid- 19 pandemic. *Asian Education and Development Studies*.
- [2] Asio, J. M. R., & Jimenez, E. (2020). Effect of remediation activities on grade 5 pupils' academic performance in technology and livelihood education (TLE). *Asio, JMR, & Jimenez, EC (2020). Effect of Remediation Activities on Grade, 5*.
- [3] Asio, J. M. R., & Riego de Dios, E. (2019). The college students' perspective on what makes an educator well-qualified. *Asio, JMR, & Riego de Dios, EE (2019). The college students' perspective on what makes an educator well-qualified. Journal of Pedagogical Research, 3(3), 126-138*.
- [4] Babalola, V. & Hafsatu, A. (2016). School administration and instructional supervision of secondary school chemistry for students' academic performance. *Issues in Scientific Research, 1 (3), 27-36*.
- [5] Bartley, S. J., & Golek, J. H. (2017). Evaluating the cost effectiveness of online and face-to-face instruction. *Educational Technology & Society, 7(4), 167-175*.
- [6] Bartanen, B., & Kwok, A. (2021). Examining clinical teaching observation scores as a measure of preservice teacher quality. *American Educational Research Journal, 58(5), 887-920*.
- [7] Bell, C. A., Dobbelaer, M. J., Klette, K., & Visscher, A. (2019). Qualities of classroom observation systems. *School effectiveness and school improvement, 30(1), 3-29*.
- [8] Blazar, D., Litke, E., & Barmore, J. (2016). What does it mean to be ranked a "high" or "low" value-added teacher? Observing differences in instructional quality across districts. *American Educational Research Journal, 53(2), 324-359*.
- [9] Bowering, E. R., Mills, J., & Merritt, A. (2017). Learning how to learn: A student success course for at risk students. *Canadian Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning, 8(3), n3*.
- [10] Butron, P. V. V. (2021). Responsiveness, emotions, and tasks of teachers in the new normal of education in the philippines. *Journal homepage: www. ijrpr. com ISSN, 2582, 7421*.
- [11] Calvin, C. (2017). Christian Aebi College Calvin, Geneva, Switzerland christian. aebi@ edu. ge. ch Grant Cairns La Trobe University, Melbourne, Australia. *INTEGERS, 17, 2*.
- [12] Campbell, S. L., & Ronfeldt, M. (2018). Observational evaluation of teachers: Measuring more than we bargained for? *American Educational Research Journal, 55(6), 1233-1267*.
- [13] Caratiquit, K., & Pablo, R. (2021). Exploring the practices of secondary school teachers in preparing for classroom observation amidst the new normal of education. *Journal of Social, Humanity, and Education*.
- [14] Cash, A. H., Hamre, B. K., Pianta, R. C., & Myers, S. S. (2017). Rater calibration when observational assessment occurs at large scale: Degree of calibration and characteristics of raters associated with calibration. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly, 27(3), 529-542*.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp: (60-74), Month: January - February 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [15] Chism, D. D. (2017). Urothelial carcinoma of the bladder and the rise of immunotherapy. *Journal of the National Comprehensive Cancer Network*, 15(10), 1277-1284.
- [16] Cohen, J., & Goldhaber, D. (2016). Building a more complete understanding of teacher evaluation using classroom observations. *Educational Researcher*, 45(6), 378-387.
- [17] Danielson, C. (2017). *Enhancing professional practice: A framework for teaching*. ASCD.
- [18] Department of Education. (2015). *DO 2, S. 2015 – Guidelines on the establishment and implementation of the results-based performance management system (RPMS) in the Department of Education*. <https://www.deped.gov.ph>
- [19] Department of Education. (2021). *[DM-PHROD-2021-0010] -Guidelines on the implementation of RPMS for SY2020-2021_signed.pdf*. GoogleDocs. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1wm6qwntEPMqP-5ZWjk1CrkZMmZbLbkj4/view>
- [20] Department of Education. (2017). *DO 42, S. 2017 – National adoption and implementation of the philippine professional standards for teachers*. <https://www.deped.gov.ph>
- [21] De Vera, J. L., Manalo, M. O., Ermeno, R. D., Carolyn, B., & Elores, Y. D. P. (2022). Teachers' instructional planning and design for learners in difficult circumstances. *Jurnal Pendidikan Progresif*, 12(1), 17-32.
- [22] Dieker, L. A., Straub, C., Hynes, M., Hughes, C. E., Bukathy, C., Bousfield, T., & Mrstik, S. (2019). Using virtual rehearsal in a simulator to impact the performance of science teachers. *International Journal of Gaming and Computer-Mediated Simulations (IJGCMS)*, 11(4), 1-20.
- [23] Dizon, A. D., San Pedro, A. B., Munsayac, M. M., Padilla, J., & Pascual, M. C. (2018). Level of implementation of the results-based performance management system in the Department of Education division of gapan city, Philippines. *International Journal of Research-GRANTHAALAYAH*, 6(1), 484-503.
- [24] Farinella, J. A., Hobbs, B. K., & Weeks, H. S. (2017). Distance delivery: The faculty perspective. *Financial Practice and Education*, 10, 184-194.
- [25] Francisco, E. B (2021). Teacher evaluation methods for effectivequalityteaching. <https://safetyculture.com/topics/teacher-evaluation/>
- [26] Gall, M. D., Borg, W. R., & Gall, J. P. (2017). *Educational research: An introduction*. Longman Publishing.
- [27] Gepila Jr, E. (2020). Assessing teachers using Philippine standards for teachers. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(3), 739-746.
- [28] Glossary of Education Reform (2018). Classroom observation. <https://www.edglossary.org/classroom-observation/>
- [29] Goldhaber, D. (2016). Exploring the potential of value-added performance measures to affect the quality of the teacher workforce. *Educational Researcher*, 44(2), 87-95.
- [30] Goldhaber, D., & Hansen, M. (2017). Is it just a bad class? Assessing the long-term stability of estimated teacher performance. *Economica*, 80(319), 589-612.
- [31] Goldhaber, D., Strunk, K., Brown, N., Chambers, A., Naito, N., & Wolff, M. (2017). Teacher staffing challenges in California: Exploring the factors that influence teacher staffing and distribution. *Getting Down to Facts II =Technical Report*, 2018-09.
- [32] Guarino, C., & Stacy, B. (2017). Review of gathering feedback for teaching: Combining high-quality observations with student surveys and achievement gains. *National Educational Policy Center*. Boulder, CO.
- [33] Gurung, S. (2021). Challenges faced by teachers in online teaching during COVID-19 pandemic. *The Online Journal of Distance Education and e- Learning*, 9(1), 8-18.
- [34] Hammersley-Fletcher, L., & Orsmond, P. (2017). Reflecting on reflective practices within peer observation. *Studies in higher education*, 30(2), 213-224.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp: (60-74), Month: January - February 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [35] Hamzah, M. I. M., Wei, Y., Ahmad, J., Hamid, A. H. A., & Mansor, A. N. (2018). Supervision Practices and Teachers' Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools: Malaysia and China. *International Education Studies*, 6(8), 92-97.
- [36] Hendry, G. D., & Oliver, G. R. (2017). Seeing is believing: The benefits of peer observation. *Journal of University Teaching & Learning Practice*, 9(1), 7.
- [37] Hew, K. F., & Cheung, W. S. (2018). Designing and implementing e-learning courses: A comparative analysis of policy guidelines from nine professional organizations. *International Journal of e-Education, e-Business, e-Management and e-Learning*, 3(3), 178.
- [38] Impof, F. (2020, November 20). Importance of lesson plan and effective lesson planning. *IMPOFF*.
- [39] Jeffery, K. A., & Bauer, C. F. (2020). Students' responses to emergency remote online teaching reveal critical factors for all teaching. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 97(9), 2472-2485.
- [40] Jewell, J. W. (2017). From inspection, supervision, and observation to value-added evaluation: A brief history of US teacher performance evaluations. *Drake L. Rev.*, 65, 363.
- [41] Kaymakamoglu, S. E. (2018). Teachers' beliefs, perceived practice and actual classroom practice in relation to traditional (teacher-centered) and constructivist (Learner-Centered) Teaching (Note 1). *Journal of Education and Learning*, 7(1), 29-37.
- [42] Kolb, A. Y., & Kolb, D. A. (2021). Experiential learning theory: A dynamic, holistic approach to management learning, education and development. *The SAGE handbook of management learning, education and development*, 42, 68.
- [43] Kraft, M. A., Blazar, D., & Hogan, D. (2018). The effect of teacher coaching on instruction and achievement: A meta-analysis of the causal evidence. *Review of educational research*, 88(4), 547-588.
- [44] Law Insider (2022). Intervention program definition. <https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/intervention-program>.
- [45] Li, C., & Lalani, F. (2020, April). The COVID-19 pandemic has changed education forever. In *World economic forum* (Vol. 29). The rise of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic | World Economic Forum (weforum.org).
- [46] Lopez, S. J., Pedrotti, J. T., & Snyder, C. R. (2018). *Positive psychology: The scientific and practical explorations of human strengths*. Sage publications.
- [47] Martinez, F., Taut, S., & Schaaf, K. (2016). Classroom observation for evaluating and improving teaching: An international perspective. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 49, 15-29.
- [48] Millis, B. J. (2017). Conducting effective peer classroom observations. *To improve the academy*, 11(1), 189-206.
- [49] Mishra, P., & Mehta, R. (2017). What we educators get wrong about 21st-century learning: Results of a survey. *Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education*, 33(1), 6-19.
- [50] Patton, M. Q. (2017). *Qualitative research & evaluation methods: Integrating theory and practice*. Sage publications.
- [51] Pianta, R. C., & Hamre, B. K. (2017). Conceptualization, measurement, and improvement of classroom processes: Standardized observation can leverage capacity. *Educational researcher*, 38(2), 109-119.
- [52] Press Center (2021). *What are the challenges faced by teachers in online education?*. https://www.viewsonic.com/in/newsroom/content/what-are-the-challenges-faced-by-teachers-in-online-education_4089_
- [53] Reyes-Chua, E., Remollo-Mack, M., & Vilorio, A. O. (2019). teachers' perceptions on the classroom peer observation exercise at eac-cavite, philippines. *European Journal of Human Resource Management Studies*.
- [54] Riego de Dios, E. (2020). Emotional intelligence and work values of selected instructors from a teacher education institution. *Riego de Dios, EE (2020). Emotional Intelligence and Work Values of Selected Instructors from a Tertiary Education Institution. International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research*, 4(5), 92-97.
- [55] Rosier, J., Slade, C., Perkins, T., Baldwin, C., Coiacetto, E., Budge, T., & Harwood, A. (2016). The benefits of embedding experiential learning in the education of planners. *Planning Practice & Research*, 31(5), 486-499.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp: (60-74), Month: January - February 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [56] Rotas, E. E., & Cahapay, M. B. (2020). Difficulties in remote learning: Voices of Philippine University Students in the Wake of COVID-19 Crisis. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(2), 147-158.
- [57] Sloat, E., Amrein-Beardsley, A., & Holloway, J. (2018). Different teacher-level effectiveness estimates, different results: inter-model concordance across six generalized value-added models (VAMs). *Educational Assessment, Evaluation and Accountability*, 30(4), 367-397.
- [58] Sullivan, P. B., Buckle, A., Nicky, G., & Atkinson, S. H. (2017). Peer observation of teaching as a faculty development tool. *BMC medical education*, 12(1), 1-6.
- [59] Suparto, S. (2020). Improving the learning quality of math teachers through the academic supervision with technique of class observation. *International Research-Based Education Journal*, 2(1), 21-24.
- [60] Tawalbeh, T. I. (2020). Instructors' perceptions of EFL supervisors' classroom observation practices at university level. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(1), 45-56.
- [61] Tayag, P. (2018). *COT (Classroom Observation Tool): Significance for Teachers*. <https://www.pressreader.com/>
- [62] Topping, K. J. (2017). Trends in peer learning. *Educational psychology*, 25(6), 631-645.
- [63] Torch (2019). Classroom Observation. <https://www.torsh.co/blog/article/classroom-observation/>
- [64] Torch, T., & Rothman, R. (2018). Rush to Judgment: Teacher evaluation in public education. Education Sector Reports. *Education Sector*.
- [65] Tyagi, H., Sabharwal, M., Dixit, N., Pal, A., & Deo, S. (2020). Leveraging providers' preferences to customize instructional content in information and communications technology-based training interventions: Retrospective analysis of a mobile phone-based intervention in india. *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 8(3), e15998.
- [66] Weisberg, D., Sexton, S., Mulhern, J., Keeling, D., Schunck, J., Palcisco, A., & Morgan, K. (2019). The widget effect: Our national failure to acknowledge and act on differences in teacher effectiveness. *New Teacher Project*.
- [67] Weli, & Bako-Osu, N. (2019). Perceived impact of supervision on classroom management of public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, River State. *International Journal of Innovative Human Ecology & Nature Studies*, 7 (4), 59-75.
- [68] Zhang, X. A., Li, N., & Harris, T. B. (2017). Putting non-work ties to work: The case of guanxi in supervisor-subordinate relationships. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 26(1), 37-54